

Digital Twin-Based 6G Testbed for Immersive Outdoor Robotics: Capacity and Latency Analysis of the Interaction with Real and Virtual Objects

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Abstract—This paper presents an experimental Digital Twin platform developed as a Beyond 5G testbed for immersive remote and autonomous driving applications for mobile robots. The testbed, deployed in UPV facilities, integrates use cases involving the immersive and cyber-physical remote driving of mobile robots, which interact with real and virtual objects. In this controlled environment, we study the capacity and latency requirements of future autonomous driving use cases based on sensor offloading to the Edge. Our study focuses on evaluating the influence of 5G communication across multiple latency sources, including video streaming, AI-assisted perception, and telecontrol. By identifying key bottlenecks in mobile robot teleoperation, this work provides insights into the latency constraints that must be addressed by future 6G networks to enable the large-scale deployment of autonomous driving across different industry verticals. The results show that, while the bottleneck of the system are the robot’s motors (up to 589.65 ms), the 360 video latency (up to 433.3 ms) and the telecontrol latency (122.5 ms) could be improved by network enhancements.

I. INTRODUCTION

In spite of the native design of autonomous vehicles to operate independently using onboard processing and AI-based decision-making, certain computationally intensive tasks require offloading to the Edge for several reasons. These reasons include optimizing route planning, reducing reaction time in unpredictable situations, introducing redundancy for critical decision validation, or minimizing hardware costs by using simpler onboard processing units [1]. Hence, autonomous driving applications require the delivery of multiple video streams, full LiDAR point clouds, and other sensor data (e.g., GNSS) from the vehicle to the Edge, stressing the uplink of the network.

To support such data flows, wireless networks must provide a demanding combination of extensive coverage, high bandwidth, low latency, and reliable connectivity that only future 6G architectures will satisfy [2]. The 6G vision targets the convergence of the human, digital, and physical worlds, providing ubiquitous connectivity to humans and machines [3]. However, 6G networks are not expected until 2030. In the meantime, private 5G networks are currently the best approach to study these demands, serving as state-of-the-art testbeds for defining the requirements of future 6G networks [4], [5].

In this context, Digital Twins present as a prominent approach of future 6G networks by creating real-time, high-fidelity digital replicas of physical vehicles and infrastructures, showcased to operators over immersive user interfaces. In industrial remote and autonomous driving applications, Digital Twins serve as a bridge to full autonomy, providing a safe test environment for validating navigation algorithms before deploying them in real-world scenarios [6], [7].

We present a Digital Twin-based testbed for immersive outdoor robotics applications in different industry verticals, designed and deployed to study the requirements of autonomous driving under 6G conditions. The testbed is built around Universitat Politecnica de Valencia (UPV) facilities and private 5G network, and integrates outdoor mobile robots teleoperated from indoor immersive cockpits. The robots interact with both real and virtual objects that have an impact on the robot behavior, representing a first step towards autonomy in a controlled environment.

The main focus of our study is to analyze the robot reaction times, by evaluating the influence of 5G communication across multiple latency sources, including video streaming, AI-assisted perception, and telecontrol. By quantifying the impact of each delay, we identify critical constraints affecting robot performance.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II summarizes the State of the Art on 6G technologies as enablers for robotics. Section III presents the System Overview, including descriptions of the Testbed Architecture and 5G Private Network. Section IV provides the Methodology for performing the analysis. Section V contains the Results and Discussion of the numerical values obtained. Finally, Section VI includes the Conclusion and Future Work.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The standardization of 6G networks is advancing through global efforts led by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), with the IMT-2030 framework serving as the foundation for next-generation mobile networks [8], [9]. However, the adoption of IMT-2020 (5G) has been slower than expected,

particularly in Europe, where businesses remain unconvinced of its advantages. The role of 5G as an enabler for mission-critical applications is not yet well-established, and its potential for enabling Digital Twins and immersive robotics remains largely untested in real-world deployments [10].

Despite these challenges, the transition towards Beyond 5G (B5G) networks has already begun, with early research focusing on defining how to implement the 6G vision, which seeks to eliminate traditional boundaries between real and virtual environments, extending connectivity and intelligence beyond what 5G enables today [3]. This evolution from IMT-2020 to IMT-2030 introduces new paradigms, in addition to expanding the previous ones: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC).

In the context of this paper, two of the most relevant 6G paradigms are "Immersive Communications" and "AI and Communication". The former extends human sensory interactions into the digital domain through technologies such as mixed reality (MR), holography, and haptic feedback. It represents an evolution of eMBB, but considering higher bandwidth and lower latency to support interactive Extended Reality (XR) experiences, allowing remote interaction between humans and robots. Meanwhile, AI and Communication serves as the bridge between human, digital, and physical domains, leveraging AI-driven networking and machine learning to create Digital Twins. These facilitate dynamic simulations, real-time network optimization, and autonomous decision-making in different industry verticals. The AI-native nature of 6G ensures that intelligence is embedded directly into the network architecture, guaranteeing automation throughout the network lifecycle.

In parallel to 3GPP, several organizations are working in the definition of common standards for the use of next-generation mobile networks in connected robotics [11]. Two examples include One6G and the Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN). One6G presented a methodology to analyse the functional requirements for various robotics use cases, by breaking down their operational phases [12]. The premise of this approach is that network requirements are different for each phase, and vary during the lifecycle of the operation. For instance, in a multi-robot autonomous driving scenario, a certain robot sending a path planning request based on sensor data offloading should be prioritized over robots that are not in a critical phase at that moment. To address these challenges, One6G proposes that the 3GPP networks store the communication requirements of each robotic operation to allocate resources accordingly. Moreover, they identify that the network latency for sensor offloading should be kept below 33 ms in uplink and 7 ms in downlink.

On the other hand, NGMN states that 6G architectures to support advanced robotics use cases should advocate for an evolutionary approach rather than a disruptive redesign. They propose that 6G should build upon the existing 5G ecosystem, leveraging software-based upgrades on current infrastructure rather than requiring an entirely new technology stack. To facilitate this evolutionary transition, NGMN has defined standardized testing frameworks to compare B5G features against state-of-the-art 5G capabilities [14]. For instance, NGMN specifies that user plane end-to-end (E2E) latency RTT should

be evaluated under a 70% of network resource load, with a target value of 10 ms considering SA configurations for eMBB (Release 15). In the case of user throughput, coverage conditions must satisfy a minimum Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) of -60 dBm and Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) of 22 dB. Under these conditions, with 100 MHz bandwidth and UL/DL ratio 1/3, the expected performance targets are 1.75 Gbps in DL (4x4 MIMO, 256 QAM) and 200 Mbps in UL (2x2 MIMO, 64 QAM).

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

In order to study the future 6G network requirements needed to support connected robotics applications, a Digital Twin-based testbed has been designed and deployed. It is deployed in the UPV campus, specifically in the outdoor velodrome and indoor immersive laboratory, both covered by a private 5G network. This testbed enables the characterization of network performance through two primary use cases.

Use Case 1 focuses on immersive remote driving, where two mobile robots are teleoperated from indoor immersive cockpits equipped with steering wheels and pedals. The operator receives real-time visual feedback via virtual reality (VR) headsets and vibro-tactile feedback through haptic vests, enhancing the situational awareness and driving experience.

Use Case 2 extends this approach by incorporating cyber-physical interaction with both real and virtual objects in the environment, moving towards the 6G vision of connected worlds. In this scenario, robots offload their sensor data (e.g., 360° video, LiDAR, and GNSS) to the Edge, where AI-based object detection and location-based augmented reality (AR) are applied. The results are then represented in a Digital Twin featuring a synchronized real-time digital replica of the environment.

A third use case is envisioned, focusing on autonomous driving using the offloaded sensor data for sensor fusion and trajectory planning. However, while this use case is considered for assessing the robot's reaction time, this paper primarily focuses on the first two use cases. Future work will address the development and validation of the autonomous driving capabilities within this testbed, including their real-world deployment and performance evaluation.

A. Testbed Architecture

The three main actors or components of the testbed, as represented in Figure 1 are outdoor mobile robots, a private 5G network, and immersive cockpits.

The robots, model Robotnik SUMMIT-XL and powered by Robot Operating System (ROS), are equipped with four 500 W brushless motors mounted on rubber wheels with skid-steering kinematics, ensuring precise movement and control. They onboard different sensors for context awareness, including Labpano Pilot One 360-degree camera, RoboSense RS-LiDAR-16, U-blox C099 Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) receiver, and several Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs). For communication, the robots onboard a Fivecomm 5G Board modem. Operating in the UPV Velodrome, they transmit real-time Digital Twin data to indoor immersive cockpits located in the UPV Immersive Lab.

Fig. 1. Testbed architecture representing real-life pictures of the three main components: 5G Network (top), with a n40 antenna covering the velodrome; Immersive Cockpits (left), displaying a Digital Twin-based user interface for enhanced teleoperation; and Mobile Robots (right), equipped with different sensors to capture their environment

The immersive cockpits feature racing seats equipped with Thurstmaster T150 wheel and pedals, Meta Quest 3 VR headsets, and bHaptics TactSuit X40 haptic vests, providing operators with a fully immersive remote driving experience. This is achieved through real-time 360 video streaming, a Digital Twin-based user interface, and haptic feedback events. Human presence within the robot’s environment is detected using AI-based object detection algorithms, specifically YOLOv9 trained to process 360 video feeds. Additionally, the video stream includes augmented reality (AR) elements and virtual power-up items that act as bonuses or penalties affecting the robot’s dynamics. These AR objects are anchored to real-world locations using GNSS data, and their effects—such as speed boosts or slowdowns—are conveyed through haptic feedback in the vest.

The Digital Twin platform is developed in Unity3D and serves as a synchronized virtual representation of the physical environment, integrating real-time robot telemetry and network status. It displays key parameters such as the robot’s position, orientation, velocity, and battery level, alongside live network indicators like signal strength, latency, throughput, and active 5G slice.

B. 5G Private Network

The 5G private network at UPV operates across three frequency bands. The n78 (sub-6GHz) band provides indoor coverage at the Immersive Laboratory, although it is not required since the cockpits use a direct connection to the 5G Core. The n40 (sub-6GHz) and n258 (mmWave) bands offer outdoor coverage for the Velodrome, but only n40 is utilized, as the n258 band is not supported by the available modems.

The Radio Access Network (RAN) configuration used in the testbed can be appreciated in Table I, following the required testing framework descriptions defined by NGMN [14]. The Core network architecture is based on Open5GS, an open-source implementation compliant with 3GPP Release 17 standards. The 5G Core deploys seven User Plane Functions (UPFs), each assigned to a specific network slice. The UPF

TABLE I. RAN CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Carrier frequency	2380 MHz
Operating bandwidth	20 MHz
Duplex mode	TDD, UL to DL slot ratio 3/7
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
Carrier prefix	NR Band: 40, ARFCN: 476000
Slot length	0.429 ms
Number of sites and UEs	1 site, 2 UEs
Type of environment	Semi-urban
Site location	Altitude: 90 m Latitude: 39.4784952 Longitude: -0.3339592
Test UEs location	Altitude: 53.814 to 55.77 m Latitude: 39.4792835 to 39.4793956 Longitude: -0.3357418 to -0.3353959
BS and UE antenna params.	BS DL Power: 26.5 dBm BS Antenna Gain: 17.1-17.6 dBi Max UE UL Power: 23 dBm UE Antenna Gain: 4 dBi
BS and UE antenna config.	4T4R (4Tx, 4Rx) Carrier Aggregation: No Maximum MCS DL: 256 QAM Maximum MCS UL: 64 QAM
MIMO layers	DL 4x4, UL 2x2
Traffic type	eMBB

Fig. 2. Latency budget including Video (encoding, network uplink and decoding), YOLO Inference, Telecontrol (Unity control and network downlink), and Braking (ROS updating of velocity topic "cmdvel", motors actuators, and ROS updating of odometry topic "odom").

selection is determined by the Data Network Name (DNN) configuration chosen by the user equipment (UE). The core database maps DNNs to slices, allowing for the application of tailored Quality of Service (QoS) parameters based on each UE’s requirements.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Latency Budget

In addition to user plane latency, the aim of this paper is to characterize the full latency budget for teleoperation, in order to discuss the network influence on the application and identify key bottlenecks that must be addressed by future 6G networks. Figure 2 displays a schema of the latency components measured. First three components (i.e., Video Latency, YOLO Inference Time, and Telecontrol Latency) depend on the 5G network and Edge computing performances, whereas the fourth component (i.e., Braking Latency) involves robotics electronics beyond the scope of the distributed mobile network.

We employ different techniques to measure delays at each critical component. First, the Video Latency is measured from camera to display, by pointing the 360 camera to a screen representing timestamps in order to take screenshots that compare the displayed timestamp with the timestamp transmitted over the 360 video stream. This latency includes capture, H265 encoding, RTSP/TCP transport, H265 decoding, and display of the video stream. The encoding process is managed by the Labpano Pilot One built-in streaming server,

which allows to configure the video quality to SD (1920x960), HD (2560x1280), or 4K (3840x1920). On the other hand, the decoding process is managed by a Gstreamer pipeline optimized with minimum latency, with the drawback that it can be sensitive to 5G network performance degradations, such as jitter and TCP retransmissions due to the absence of buffer that would increase the latency. To analyze the impact of congestion, the measurements are taken first for a single user (i.e., one video stream at the time) and then for a multi-user scenario (i.e., two video streams in parallel), taking 20 samples for each combination of resolution and number of user equipments (UEs). The Video Latency measurements were taken in the n78 indoor network covering the Immersive Laboratory in order to guarantee sufficient bandwidth to support two 4K video streams.

Second, the YOLO Inference Time is measured by timing the forward pass of the model, which includes the time taken by the neural network to detect a physical object (i.e., a pedestrian) and generate the bounding box. This excludes preprocessing and postprocessing times such as resizing the video frames and formatting the results, but those values are considered to be negligible. The YOLO configuration used is YOLOv9-C running on an NVIDIA RTX 3080, with input image resolution of 640x320 in order to maintain the original aspect ratio. At the moment, no execution optimizations are being applied, though optimization is possible. The model has been trained on a custom dataset to detect pedestrians in the velodrome using 360 camera imagery, as available models are usually trained for conventional cameras. Evaluation on detection accuracy was also performed considering Ultralytics

Third, the Telecontrol Latency is calculated by embedding timestamps into the Unity code. Once the user application executed in the cockpit detects that the robot is interacting with either a real object (i.e., YOLO-based pedestrian detection) or a virtual object (i.e., AR obstacle positioned in the Digital Twin based on GNSS information), it sends a telecontrol command to the robot to stop the robot. Note that the communication of GNSS information from the robot to the Unity code is not being considered for the latency budget since it is negligible in comparison with the Video Latency, and therefore we chose to evaluate the worst case scenario. In any case, the Telecontrol Latency encompasses the delay from the object interaction to the ACK reception from the robot published on the velocity topic of ROS.

Fourth, the braking latency involves the ROS processes of reading the updated velocity topic, applying the brake to the robot's electrical motor wheels (which depends on the speed of the robot before braking), and publishing a second ACK on the odometry topic of ROS to let the cockpit know that the robot has stopped. Similar to the other components, the measurement procedure consists in adding timestamps to the code for monitoring the mentioned ROS topics. The velocities of the robot before braking considered to take the measurements are 1, 1.5, 2 and 2.5 m/s.

Finally, the end to end (E2E) is calculated by adding these fourth main latency components. By analyzing the E2E latency for each velocity, we can also obtain the braking distance of the robot. In addition, the user perceived latency should also include again the video latency since it is the primary feedback

the user receives. However, the aim of this analysis is to study the latency budget from the robot's perspective, considering a future autonomous driving application where the robot's reaction time must be minimized. We use a controlled remote driving environment to simulate such scenario, where the sensor data offloading must be performed with the minimum possible delay to minimize the braking distance.

B. Network Limitations

Although the focus of our study is latency, it is also necessary to assess the throughput capacity of the network (specially in UL), since the use cases deployed in the testbed require the delivery of two 360 video streams with varying requirements depending on the quality. The throughput generated by each 360 camera is 5 Mbps in SD (1920x960), 8 Mbps in HD (2560x1280), or 15 Mbps in 4K (3840x1920). Hence, for two mobile robots streaming the maximum quality, up to 30 Mbps of uplink throughput are required. Moreover, congestion scenarios due to the inability of the network to satisfy the throughput requirements of the two video streams are expected to result in packet retransmission and latency increase.

In comparison with NGMN testing framework for assessing network performance metrics [14], our RAN is limited by lower operating bandwidth (20 MHz vs 100 MHz), lack of carrier aggregation, and UE's efficiency (3GPP 38.306 scaling factor) of 0.75, although the TDD pattern configured is slightly superior for UL (3/7 vs 1/3). These differences result in a lower theoretical user throughput and end-to-end (E2E) user plane latency. According to 3GPP TS 38.306 calculations, the expected theoretical capacity of our network is 229.21 Mbps in DL and 39.41 Mbps in UL. In contrast, NGMN claimed expected values of 1.75 Gbps in DL and 200 Mbps in UL, as stated in Section II. The primary throughput reduction comes from the narrower bandwidth (20%), followed by the scaling factor (75%). Additionally, the TDD pattern slightly lowers DL capacity (93.3%) but improves UL performance (120%). It is also necessary to consider that NGMN defines this metrics for ideal coverage conditions (i.e., RSRP of -60dBm, SINR of 22 dB), whereas the conditions in the velodrome can vary depending on the location.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Latency Evaluation

The results of the latency evaluation can be appreciated in Figure 3. The Video Latency results highlight the impact of video resolution and the number of parallel video streams communicated over the 5G private network. With a single User Equipment (UE), latency averages 301.4 ms in SD, 366.95 ms in HD, and 470.95 ms in 4K. This indicates that a higher resolution introduces a significant encoding, transmission, and decoding delay. When two UEs are streaming simultaneously, the latency rises to 433.3 ms in SD, 536.14 ms in HD, and 567.15 ms in 4K, suggesting network congestion for which the current video streaming protocol (i.e., RTSP over TCP) is not prepared.

The YOLO Inference Time averages 21.57 ms, which are negligible compared to the Video Latency. Although execution optimizations could be applied, the forward pass of the model has a low delay due to the use of an input image of low

Fig. 3. Latency budget results, divided in Video Latency (top left) at different qualities and number of cameras streaming, Telecontrol Latency (top right), YOLO Inference Time (bottom left), and Braking Latency (bottom right) at different speeds.

resolution (640x320). Considering the YOLO resolution, the SD and 2UEs configuration of the video streaming will be selected for calculating the total latency.

The Telecontrol Latency averages 122.5 ms with considerable variability, since the publish frequency of the ROS cmdvel topic is fixed to 10 Hz, which gives a measurement error of up to 100 ms. This latency should be optimized both from the application and network levels, considering that low traffic throughput (i.e., in the order of kbps) is being generated.

By adding the Video, YOLO, and Telecontrol latencies (as represented in Equation 1), we obtain an average offloading latency of 577.37 ms, which represents the reaction time of the robot with obstacle detection processed in the Edge of the private 5G network. If the braking action is also considered, we can calculate the braking distance required for an autonomous vehicle, depending on the speed it was circulating when the obstacle was detected (as represented in Table II). The total latency can increase up to 1167.02 ms considering the maximum speed of the robot, which translates into a braking distance of 2.92 m. This value highlights the necessity of optimizing the offloading process by the use of more efficient communication and processing.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{\text{Total}} &\approx L_{\text{Video}} + L_{\text{YOLO}} + L_{\text{Telecontrol}} + L_{\text{Braking}} \\
 &\approx 433.3 + 21.57 + 122.5 + L_{\text{Braking}} \\
 &\approx 577.37 \text{ ms} + L_{\text{Braking}}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

TABLE II. BRAKING DISTANCE AS A FUNCTION OF THE ROBOT'S SPEED

Speed (m/s)	Braking Latency (ms)	Total Latency (ms)	Braking Distance (m)
1.0	255.21	832.58	0.83
1.5	359.53	936.9	1.41
2.0	471.08	1048.46	2.1
2.5	589.65	1167.02	2.92

The offloading latency is primarily driven by video streaming delays, which could be mitigated by the use of 6G Quality of Service (QoS) mechanisms that simultaneously guarantee low latency and high throughput in a multi-user environment. Moreover, the use of optimized, network-robust protocols could further minimize encoding/decoding and transmission latency, making real-time 360 video streaming more viable.

Fig. 4. n40 band parameter evolution around the velodrome. RSRP (top left) and SINR (top right) values measured in n40 band around the Velodrome outdoor scenario, averaging a -75.3 dBm and a 21.9 dB respectively; compared to Throughput UL (bottom left) and DL (bottom right) averaging 19.6 Mbps and 102.2 Mbps respectively.

In general, future 6G networks could drastically reduce these delays by integrating 6G-native edge computing, as well as implementing HRLLC (Hyper-Reliable Low-Latency Communication) and AI-enhanced network slicing.

B. Network Evaluation

A combined coverage and capacity drive test was performed on the n40 band around the velodrome, with the results represented in Figure 4. The average RSRP of -75.3 dBm and SINR of 21.9 dB only suppose a slight degradation in comparison to the NGMN-defined ideal conditions (i.e., RSRP of -60 dBm and SINR of 22 dB) [14]. However, the eastern part of the velodrome suffers from signal degradation (i.e., RSRP of -85 dBm, SINR of 0 dB), possibly due to non-line-of-sight conditions between the 5G antenna and the User Equipment (UE). Apparently, the signal degradation does not translate into capacity degradation since the Throughput obtained consistently averaged 19.6 Mbps in UL and 102.2 Mbps in DL. In comparison to 3GPP TS 38.306 calculations for theoretical capacity (i.e., 39.4 Mbps in UL and 229.2 Mbps in DL), the real capacity is reduced by a 50%, possibly due to problems in the MIMO configuration.

Nonetheless, the real capacity of the network is sufficient to support the video streaming configuration (i.e., SD and 2UEs) required by the YOLO object detection system. The two video streams impose a 51% of network resource load, which is close to the NGMN reference of 70% [14]. Thus, the round trip time (RTT) user plane latency calculated averages 32.72 ms, as displayed in Figure 5. Assuming network symmetry in UL/DL, the one-way latency is 16.36 ms. It can be observed that, apparently, this value is only 3.77% of Video Latency, 13.36% of Telecontrol Latency and 5.66% of offloading latency. Nonetheless, 6G can significantly reduce total system latency beyond just transport delay by optimizing network-aware video processing, and predictive telecontrol mechanisms. In 5G, video buffering is required to handle jitter and packet reordering, whereas 6G's AI-driven congestion control and predictive buffering can minimize this overhead. Furthermore, 6G's Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) could substitute the video-based perception for radio-based perception, eliminating video delays.

Fig. 5. Round Trip Time (RTT) latency of the private 5G network evaluated under a 51% of network resource load

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We presented a Digital Twin-enabled and advanced 5G-based testbed for immersive outdoor robotics, characterizing the E2E latency under realistic teleoperation conditions. The testbed integrates mobile robots operating in a controlled outdoor environment at Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), combining 360 video streaming, YOLO-based AI object detection, and location-based AR objects within a Digital Twin interface. This study provides a breakdown of system-level latencies, covering video streaming, AI inference, telecontrol commands, and physical braking, offering insights of current 5G capabilities and highlighting the requirements for future 6G networks to support autonomous driving use cases. The 5G private network tested, although limited in bandwidth (20 MHz), is representative of a realistic 6G deployment in terms of application-layer requirements, whereas it may be limited to assess the scalability of 6G considering a multi-robot scenario.

The latency analysis reveals that video streaming is the primary bottleneck, with measured latencies ranging from 301.4 ms (SD) to 470.95 ms (4K) in a single-user scenario, and rising to 433.3 ms (SD) to 567.15 ms (4K) when two users stream simultaneously. This suggests that network congestion and streaming inefficiencies substantially impact end-to-end (E2E) delay. Telecontrol latency (122.5 ms) and YOLO inference time (21.57 ms) are negligible in comparison, indicating that optimizing the Unity-ROS communication and AI modules would have minimal impact on overall system performance. The total offloading latency averages 577.37 ms, increasing up to 1167.02 ms when braking delays are included, which directly impacts reaction times and braking distances in autonomous robotic applications. The network itself demonstrated stable uplink (19.6 Mbps) and downlink (102.2 Mbps) throughput, with an RTT of 32.72 ms, indicating that network transport is not the limiting factor, but rather application-level inefficiencies such as the streaming protocol.

To address these challenges, future work will focus on concrete system-level optimizations, such as adopting WebRTC or QUIC-based streaming protocols, implementing optimized encoding pipelines, and experimenting with video compression tailored for 360 video (e.g., viewport streaming). Moreover, the use of conventional cameras will be explored as an alternative to 360 streaming, analyzing the trade-off between reduced latency and diminished situational awareness resulting from a narrower field of view. Additionally, a comparative evalu-

ation between end-to-end latency and network delay will be conducted under varied traffic conditions to better understand the impact of the network, including a deeper analysis of jitter and packet loss, which are critical for maintaining stability and responsiveness in real-time autonomous operations. In parallel, we will expand the system toward full autonomy by integrating sensor fusion and digital twin-based trajectory planning, while leveraging 6G-native features such as Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC). These developments aim to bridge the performance and reliability gap between current 5G robotics and future 6G cyber-physical systems, providing a reproducible experimental framework for the next generation of autonomous mobile systems.

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